

Applications of Compton Imaging in Nuclear Waste Characterization and Treaty Verification

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Abstract

Compton imaging systems have a number of advantages for characterization of nuclear waste, such as identifying hot spots in mixed waste in order to reduce the volume of high-level waste requiring extensive treatment or long-term storage, and imaging large objects or contaminated areas.

Compton imaging also has potential applications for monitoring production, deployment, shipping and storage of nuclear warheads and components in the verification of treaties such as START I and II, the Comprehensive Test Ban Treaty and the Non-Proliferation Treaty.

This article presents a brief historical perspective and discusses system design requirements and performance specifications for these applications. The advantages of Compton imaging are compared to competing imaging technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Compton imaging systems, also known as Compton cameras, make use of the kinematics of Compton scattering to reconstruct a gamma-ray source image without the use of collimators or masks. Compton cameras typically consist of two or more planes of detectors separated by the order of 10 cm to 1 m. An event consists of a detection of the energy and position of a Compton scattering in the front plane, followed by detection of the residual energy and position of the scattered gamma ray in the back plane. This defines the initial gamma-ray energy and the scattering angle. Backprojection of multiple events allows the reconstruction of the source image.

The advantages of Compton cameras over conventional imaging techniques include a large field-of-view, increased efficiency and good background suppression. Compton cameras are effective over a large energy range (140 to 10,000 keV) and can be used in an energy selective mode to separately image mixed gamma-ray sources. At close ranges (out to a few meters) they are capable of 3D imaging from a fixed position. A recent article reviews the history and principles of Compton imaging in more detail and discusses current applications and future prospects [1].

The first Compton camera was designed for medical imaging as a replacement for heavy lead collimators in SPECT using 140 keV gamma rays [2]. The use of a 4x4 germanium detector for the front plane and a large position sensitive NaI detector for the back plane provided an improvement in sensitivity by a factor of 25 over conventional SPECT [3]. A system in which the back detector was replaced by an array of NaI detectors achieved a resolution of 1.5 cm for 662 keV gamma-rays [4].

Recently, three-dimensional imaging of an array of sources with different energies and intensities was demonstrated using germanium detector arrays for both the front and back planes [5],[6].

II. APPLICATIONS

A. Gamma Rays of Interest

For treaty verification and nuclear waste characterization the gamma rays of interest are generally those from nuclear warhead materials and nuclear reactor fuels and byproducts. These are listed in Table 1.

All of the nuclides in the first section of the table are typically seen in nuclear material that has been in a reactor and are also present in varying amounts in nuclear weapons. The most difficult to detect and identify is highly enriched ^{235}U because of its low-energy gamma rays, which are easily shielded. The characteristic 375 and 414 keV gamma rays from ^{239}Pu are less easily shielded and lie in the effective range for Compton imaging as do the penetrating high-energy gamma rays from ^{238}U and ^{232}U .

Reactor waste that has been in storage long enough for the short halflife fission products to decay is characterized by the 662 keV gamma ray from ^{137}Cs and the complex of gamma rays from $^{152,154}\text{Eu}$. The penetrating ^{60}Co gamma rays are the result of activation of stainless steel.

Table 1
Gamma Rays of Interest

Nuclide (halflife)	Gamma rays [decay chain nuclide]
Nuclear fuels and nuclear warhead materials	
^{232}U (69y)	583, 2615 keV [from ^{208}Tl], also in natural background from decay of ^{232}Th
^{235}U (7.0E8y)	186 keV
^{238}U (4.5E9y)	766, 1001 keV
^{239}Pu (2.4E4y)	375, 414 keV
^{241}Pu (14y)	208, 662, 723 keV [from ^{241}Am (433y)]
Long lived fission products	
^{137}Cs (30y)	662 keV
^{152}Eu (13y)	344, 779, 964, 1112, 1408
^{154}Eu (8.8y)	723, 873, 996, 1005, 1274
Neutron activation products	
^{60}Co (5.3 y)	1173, 1332 keV

Although Compton imaging has been demonstrated at energies as low as 140 keV for SPECT, it is most practical for energies above 300 keV up to several thousand keV. At low energies collimators or masks may be more effective, but these are impractical above a few hundred keV. A combined instrument has been proposed which uses a coded aperture mask in front of a germanium strip detector array for imaging low energy gamma rays and a second back array for use as a Compton camera for imaging higher energy gamma rays [7].

B. Treaty Verification

A number of treaties are in various stages of negotiation, ratification and implementation, which involve limitations on the production deployment and testing of nuclear weapons. These include the START treaty limiting deployment of nuclear armed ballistic missiles, the START II treaty for elimination of heavy ICBMs, the Comprehensive Test Ban treaty and the Non-Proliferation treaty. Compton imaging can be useful in treaty verification applications for identifying and counting warheads or components and for inspecting cargo containers for transport of nuclear materials. However, it has to be carefully applied to satisfy the often conflicting demands of assuring treaty compliance while limiting intrusiveness. That is, it has to obtain enough information to make sure neither side is cheating while at the same time not reveal classified weapon design information. This requires hardware and software constraints, which are discussed further in the section on design considerations.

Compton imaging could be applied for counting the number of nuclear warheads carried on a missile without removing the missile casing and for counting the number of warheads or warhead components in storage without opening the storage containers. Advantages of Compton imaging for these applications include the ability to detect and image the higher energy gamma rays from Table I, which can penetrate container walls, and shielding. Selecting only those full-energy gamma rays that penetrate the shielding can provide good suppression of interference due to scattered gamma rays that are degraded in energy and in position information.

Compton imaging could also be used to inspect suspect containers for nuclear weapons or materials being transported in violation of the Non-Proliferation treaty. The ability to obtain an image of a large object from a fixed viewpoint is a significant advantage over other imaging techniques that require scanning of the container.

C. Nuclear Waste Management

The US classifies nuclear waste as high level waste (HLW), which is generally spent nuclear fuel and transuranic materials (TRU), and low level waste (LLW) with activities less than 100 nCi/g, which is generally contaminated equipment and materials. The large volumes of waste currently in storage must be characterized as HLW or LLW before going into long term storage or disposal. Compton imaging can be used to identify hot spots in barrels of waste which can then be removed, allowing the remaining material to be disposed of at much less expense as LLW.

Compton imaging can also be used for mapping of large contaminated objects, structures or sites. It can identify hot spots on a contaminated wall or floor allowing them to be removed for separate disposal before renovation or demolition of the building. It can also be used overhead in a crane or helicopter to identify and characterize contaminated sites.

III. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

A. Technical Challenges

There are a number of technical challenges which must be met in order to produce a practical compact Compton camera with real time imaging capabilities for applications in nuclear waste management and treaty verification. Technical advances being developed for consumer, medical, industrial and space applications will help to make a practical Compton imaging system a reality.

Image resolution depends both on the energy resolution of the detectors and on the position resolution. This requires large detector arrays with both good energy resolution of 1% or less and good detection efficiency. These requirements are easily met by germanium detector arrays, but they require cooling to temperatures below 100 K. Liquid nitrogen cooling is not always convenient for nuclear waste applications and may not be readily available at treaty verification sites. The alternative of mechanical cooling adds power requirements and weight to the system.

Room temperature semiconductor detectors such as CdZnTe show promise of approaching 1% energy resolution. Further development is needed to produce high-resolution detectors in sizes large enough to stop the high-energy gamma rays necessary for imaging nuclear materials and nuclear wastes.

Position resolution depends both on the size of the individual detector elements (or pixels) and the separation of the two detector planes. At one-meter separation, a pixel size of 1 cm for the individual detector elements in the array will give a position resolution of about 1%. For a more compact system, smaller pixel size is needed. For a given pixel size, a larger number of pixels increases the efficiency and reduces the problem of image artifacts but adds to the complexity and cost.

The angular uncertainty for a gamma ray which scatters at an angle θ , is inversely proportional to $\sin(\theta)$, so small angle scatterings degrade image resolution and should be rejected. This suggests a sparse detector array with widely separated pixels. A sparse array would also reduce cross talk due to scattering of a gamma ray into an adjacent pixel.

The requirement for a large number of detector array elements greatly increases the number of amplifiers, ADCs and logic elements. This will require the use of application specific integrated circuits, which have been developed for space and industrial applications in order to reduce both power and weight requirements.

Real-time imaging requires fast efficient computer algorithms. The rapid advance in computer processing power along with the application of efficient parallel

algorithms developed for medical imaging should satisfy this requirement.

B. Application Specific Design Issues

The design of a Compton imaging system can be tailored to the application. For characterization of nuclear waste barrels a resolution of a cubic centimeter is required. For wall scanning or site mapping, a much larger resolution may be sufficient. In treaty verification, the resolution capabilities of the system can be designed to limit intrusiveness. For warhead counting the position resolution need only be somewhat less than the separation of the warheads in order to reduce concerns that it could reveal classified information. The capability of acquiring a high-resolution gamma-ray spectrum also raises concern about revealing design information. For Compton imaging it is not necessary to acquire a spectrum if the gamma rays of interest are known and the data acquisition system can be limited by hardware and software design to preclude this capability.

C. Competing Technologies

There are a number of other imaging technologies that can be competitive with Compton imaging depending on the application. The multiple pinhole camera is a mature technology with good image resolution and is still used in applications such as SPECT where there is a single low-energy gamma ray of known energy. However it is limited to a few hundred keV in gamma-ray energy and it requires heavy collimation with small aperture size. For low-level sources it requires relatively long counting times.

Collimated germanium detectors provide much improved energy resolution over the position sensitive NaI detectors used in multiple pinhole cameras, however the other limitations still apply. A coded aperture mask provides an improved efficiency and field of view over a pinhole collimator and can be combined with Compton imaging to cover a broader energy range.

Active computed tomography (CT) of nuclear waste barrels provides a detailed image of the material densities in the barrel. However it requires scanning of the object and access to both sides and it does not image the nuclear materials. Passive CT obtains an image from the gamma-rays emitted by the nuclear materials but it requires scanning and very long counting times to image low-level wastes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Compton imaging has unique advantages for applications to nuclear waste characterization and treaty verification. It is completely passive and can obtain a 3D image of an object from a single viewpoint without scanning or access to both sides of the object. It covers a large energy range, has an intrinsically wide field of view and requires no collimation. It can separate mixed radionuclide sources by selectively imaging the gamma rays of interest and provides good background suppression through the kinematics of the scattering process and through energy filtering.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. W. Phillips, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research*, vol. B99, pp. 674-677, 1995.
- [2] M. Singh and D. Doria, *Medical Physics*, vol. 123, pp. 428-435, 1983.
- [3] M. Singh and R.R. Brechner, *Journal of Nuclear Medicine*, vol. 31, pp. 178-186, 1990.
- [4] J.B. Martin et al., *IEEE Transactions in Nuclear Science*, vol. NS-41, pp. 1019-1025, 1994.
- [5] J.E. McKisson, et al., *IEEE Transactions in Nuclear Science*, vol. NS-41, pp. 1221-1224, 1994.
- [6] S.E. King et al., *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research*, vol. A133, pp. 320-323, 1994.
- [7] B.F. Philips et al., *IEEE Transactions in Nuclear Science*, vol. NS-43, pp. 1472-1475, 1996.